

IMPROVING PRESERVATION AND ACCESS TO BORN-DIGITAL COLLECTIONS: A CRITICAL DISABILITY AND INTERSECTIONALITY-INFORMED ASSESSMENT OF PRAXIS

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Abstract - As with most technologies, computers were invented and designed by the status quo with the status quo in mind as the primary users. As such, there are implicit, systemic, and unconscious biases built into hardware and software which can have unintended consequences. The steady increase of born-digital records in archival collections challenges practitioners' abilities to steward these resources in ways that authentically preserve them while simultaneously accommodating them to fit users' various needs. Leveraging the frameworks from Critical Disability Theory and Intersectionality Theory, the author identifies examples of historic and current biases that are present in computing design. She provides suggestions for mindful modification of digital preservation, processing, and access workflows to account for said biases and attempt to improve the user experience.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The variabilities across born-digital archival content and each repository's collections creates a myriad of challenges for preserving and providing access to cultural heritage resources. As they are

natively electronic, there are both opportunities and hindrances for born-digital collection management and access. Computer hardware and software design, algorithms, and metadata implicitly impact equitable preservation and access to the ever-increasing amounts of born-digital acquisitions. By analyzing the limitations of both obsolete and current technologies through the lens of Critical Disability and Intersectionality Theories, this paper seeks to leverage the knowledge about the technical limitations and inherent biases of computers in order to improve preservation and access of born-digital resources.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Evaluating links between disability studies and intersectionality with library science, and in particular digital preservation and born-digital archives, requires a breadth of assessments to gain an understanding of the research. As noted by Emma May in their comprehensive literature review of these subjects, "the field of critical disability studies has seldom converged with LIS research." [32]

Computer science began studying biases and impacts on users in the 1990s, just as many countries were beginning to pass legislation to aid citizens with

disabilities in both tangible environments and through technologies.[16] Yet with stored-program-computers coming onto the scene in the 1940s, that left nearly a fifty year gap between user adoption and study of bias in computing. In 1996, Batya Friedman and Helen Nissenbaum created a three-part framework for identifying the biases in computing using an interdisciplinary approach based on Friedman's background in mathematics and computer science and Nissenbaum's background in philosophy.[19] They defined Preexisting Bias as those elements rooted in institutions, practices, and attitudes and that they may originate in any form from society at large to an individual organization. Technical Bias arises from technological constraints such as those found in tools, algorithms, or pseudorandom number generation. Lastly, Emerging Bias results in user interactions with computing, often when updated or new societal knowledge may inform perspectives. Emerging Bias can also manifest when actual user experience does not match the perceived use by designers. By framing and defining these three forms of bias, Friedman and Nissenbaum underscored the importance of computer design criteria to hold freedom from bias as an ideal with continuous reassessment. Friedman and Nissenbaum also determined from their findings that avoiding a particular form of bias in design can also lead to other biases, both consciously and unconsciously.[19]

Others in various fields of scholarship have gone on to continuously address the preexisting, technical, and emergent biases of computer hardware and software design. For example, in their book on the history of computing in Britain, Mar Hooks documents how Britain went from leading electronic computing after World War II to a swift decline by the mid-1970s due to labor mismanagement because of gender discrimination. Hicks argues that there is evidence women technologists were at the forefront of computer science but that they had been consistently relegated to lower status positions, sidelined, and denied achievements. As such, Hicks illustrates how institutional biases, such as sexism, had long-lasting and unintended consequences on computing.[24] Additionally, in recent years, there has been an increase in assessments of algorithmic biases in software, including machine learning and artificial intelligence [6] [8] [13] [38], which speaks to the

concerns of addressing bias in design to offset both preexisting and technical biases.

Much of the LIS research and guidelines focus on physical accessibility [1] [21] [27] [32] [33] [35], and there is need to expand these studies to digital collections. Because of the 2024 updated requirements for public institutions in the United States to require compliance with web accessibility guidelines [2], there is a growing trend to develop procedures for reducing these barriers at the onset of publishing content online as well as swiftly complying with accommodation requests.[13] [38] Therefore, it is probable that the profession will begin to see more case studies and case law about how accommodations are met for digital collections.

Archives and special collections repositories have trended towards inclusivity practices across all sectors of their work in the last decade.[9] [10] [12] [31] The growing consensus is that holdings can be better highlighted and made available to provide authentic voices for the most marginalized communities.[31] Through both active collecting and increased primary source literacy instruction, archives have found tools to educate users about archival silences, which are absences of representations from marginalized or othered communities in the preserved records.[9] [12] [31] Much of the current work on archival silence education centers on non-digital formats. As such, there are fewer case studies which include assessments of digitized and born-digital materials that measure inclusivity practices with these formats.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Critical Disability (CDT) and Intersectionality Theories provide constructive frameworks for analyzing the challenges that computing history has had on the management of and access to archival born-digital collections. CDT posits that disability is a social construct and that the disadvantages faced by those with physical, cognitive, and mental disabilities are the result of ableist perspectives and design.[9] [23] [32] Rooted in practical action, CDT seeks to correct these disadvantages to improve the outcomes and lives of those with disabilities.[23]

Intersectionality Theory examines how overlapping social identities and circumstances are related to and the byproduct of various disadvantages and discrimination.[15] Intersectionality is closely related to other theoretical

frameworks which seek to examine influential power structures and social inequities for example, Affect Theory, Critical Race Theory, Feminist Theory, Postcolonial Theory, and Queer Theory.[9] As such, Intersectionality builds on the understanding of these identity markers by demonstrating that they often do not exist independently.[15] Similar to CDT, these social construct theories and Intersectionality Theory make calls to action to remediate the disadvantages faced by those considered other, abnormal, or a minority.[15] [31]

A. Definitions

Employing the lens of these theories, I seek to demonstrate how biases exist in computing and their impacts on born-digital resources. Throughout the paper, I will use the term “accessibility” to encompass all the degrees by which products, devices, services, environments, or facilities are usable to people physically, cognitively, and emotionally. “Ableism” is a bias rooted in the idea that those with full able-body physicality and sound mental health are superior to those with physical, cognitive, or mental impairments; further, it insinuates that those with such impairments should be remedied rather than be presented with accommodations.[23] “Bigotry” often has the formal definition as an intentional intolerance of differences. However, utilizing the lenses of CDT and Intersectionality, I broaden the term to encompass all the ways in which intentional, systemic, and unconscious beliefs cause oppressions based on various identities and circumstances.

IV. COMPUTING BIAS: ABLEISM

Ableism has underscored the design and assumptions about use in both computer hardware and software. The aim of these machines was built on the notion that users would have full vision, auditory functions, limb symmetry, full control over all physical aspects of their body, English-language reading ability and comprehension, as well as a mid-to-high level of cognitive function. Instead, assistive technologies, which are tools that help improve functionality for those with disabilities, were developed and adopted across many systems to modify the original designs of hardware and software.[3] [11]

There are many different features found in computing product design that are examples of unintentional disadvantages to users. Visual information is displayed through a monitor, such as

its contrast, colors, and size, which can adversely affect those with vision or sensory issues. The keyboard and mouse were designed with right-handed people in mind which was a disadvantage to approximately ten percent of the global population. Additionally, peripherals, such as keyboards and pointing devices (i.e., mice), could not originally be used by those with physical impairments or those with limb differences. Computers also often rely on audio output to convey information through a variety of audiovisual resources for the system and files. Yet as a core component of the machine, developers did not take into account the reality that an estimated twenty percent of the global population suffer from hearing-related challenges or loss.

Historically, the initial design of computer software did not have the adaptability to work for those with common physical disabilities like hearing and visual impairments. In 1986, Jim Thatcher of IBM created a screen reader for staff members, but it was not widely available for the public.[14] Indeed, laws around the globe did not guarantee rights to those with disabilities until the 1980s. The United States passed its American Disabilities Act in 1990, enshrining rights for those with disabilities to have equitable access to opportunities in their public lives. After the late 1980s and early 1990s, many more countries began to enact similar laws which additionally influenced the global product market and the product design of computers.[16] While it is notable that many assistive technologies were introduced at this time and have been iterated on since, it is worth noting that historic software in particular is full of idiosyncrasies. Much of early software was not standardized across operating systems and versions, making it challenging for normalizing the integration of assistive technologies. When software was designed with assistive technologies in mind, adequate metadata may not have been embedded in the appropriate places to render it correctly.

V. COMPUTING BIAS: BIGOTRY

Ruha Benjamin succinctly describes a commonly overlooked issue with computing: “technologies, which often pose as objective, scientific, or progressive, too often reinforce racism and other forms of inequity.”[6] The people who first created hardware and software, refined, and developed it largely represent a group of cishet, white, American men. While unintentional, the dominance of this

culture in computing has shaped the hardware and software through a narrow lens. These initial biases have been intangible and are easily overlooked.[8] [19] [20] [34] Nonetheless, they have systemic effects that continue to impact computing biases; Benjamin dubs this phenomenon the “New Jim Code:” “the employment of new technologies that reflect and reproduce existing inequities but that are promoted and perceived as more objective or progressive than the discriminatory systems of a previous era.”[6]

Software development has also become increasingly dependent on algorithms, machine learning, and artificial intelligence. As a result, any initial biases in the code could be sustained or grow rather than mitigated.[19] [34] The training data that informs the coding of algorithms is often not from a comprehensive and inclusive pool. As such, recurring training of the code can be favorable to only a specific set of persons or subjects while unintentionally isolating others.[6] [34] For example, bigotry in computing can be demonstrated in situations where developers failed to include persons of color’s lived experiences into training data. As recently as 2015 when Apple was developing speech recognition for its virtual assistant, Siri, they initially excluded dialects, like African American Vernacular English (AAVE).[29] This choice reduced equitable functions of their product and its potential for growth. Additionally, algorithms assessing autism diagnoses have been built on the notion that the behaviors of those with autism are fundamentally abnormal and should be corrected. The flaws of these algorithms instead pre-categorized their statuses as something to be fixed rather than supported.[34]

VI. BIAS IMPACTS ON BORN-DIGITAL COLLECTIONS

Born-digital archives are unique cultural heritage resources that act as authentic evidence of history. In contrast to paper-based archives, born-digital materials can be simpler to recreate and share due to the inherent copy + paste functionality of data. Yet they should not be modified unless absolutely necessary to avoid losing any vital information and to verify the legitimacy of the records. However, bias encroaches on natively electronic resources in ways that are not always readily obvious.

For example, a more recent text document or web resource will likely have embedded tagging and styling applied allowing for ease of use with assistive technologies, such as a screen reader. In contrast, an

early text document, for example from the 1980s, is less likely to include such embedded metadata as these standards were not enforced in the United States until the passing of the Web Accessibility Guidelines in 1999.[37]

While it is tempting to automatically apply accessibility structure to historic documents in an effort to reduce bias and barriers, archival workers should be mindful of inadvertently altering the historic record without transparency. Derivative copies are the best option for making adjustments to combat biases. Yet because these documents were not originally designed for embedded accessibility tagging, it is resource and time intensive to apply these settings to every historic document. Many opportunities for reducing time intensive alterations to derivative records exist in theory and practice with emerging generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools. For example, automatic talk-to-text tools can quickly generate transcriptions as external text documents and as embedded metadata, such as subtitles in an audiovisual file. Yet introducing generative AI solutions in archival workflows need to be met with documentation, transparency, and caveats; if solutions are used to improve accessibility, limitations of the software and a mechanism for reporting errors and solutions must be in place prior to committing to the tools’ integration.

Additionally, archival workers should assess whether a user needs to compare an accessible, derivative version to an original copy in the collection. Staff will need to determine whether they should keep more than one derivative, such as one altered with accessibility and one unaltered, for researchers’ comparison, or whether they are instead prepared to generate these requests on demand. Relatedly, users may need access to metadata and documentation about processing to verify the authenticity of a document they are viewing and archival workers will need to determine whether their workflows account for accommodating these requests as well.

Similarly, the technical feasibilities of born-digital data can hinder the scalability of accessibility workflows. Some born-digital archives contain hundreds of thousands of discrete files. As such, there are challenges for staff to effectively work through the majority of files and make comprehensive determinations about the biases and insensitivities present in the collection. The sheer quantity and complexity of the files, their formats,

age, and dependencies on specific hardware, software, or operating systems all reduce the likelihood of noticing biases, let alone remediating them, before the content is shared with the users. Again, there is rising potential to scale these efforts through generative AI tools, yet many currently only focus on specific file formats, such as text documents and still images.

By comprehending that born-digital collections are subjected to inherent biases of computing, we can further design and evolve our practices to work within the limitations of these technologies and be transparent about our custodial choices.

VII. POTENTIAL BIAS REMEDIATIONS

B. *Digital Preservation*

Digital preservation actions require consistent work on the authenticity, reliability, and integrity of digital collections. Many repositories scale their preservation activities, i.e., into levels, as there is no single, standardized method for managing and preserving assets. Accessibility is already a common pillar in designing and executing digital preservation actions.[17] [30] However, there are additional methods we can employ to expand standards and reduce barriers due to inherent biases of computing. Knowing we need to be prepared to meet a variety of needs based on accessibility and bigoted biases, we should not be rigid in our preservation standards. Flexible approaches to these workflows will provide the ability to make modifications to the data for users both proactively and as requested.

Consider how many copies of an item and its derivative forms to store responsibly. This involves a holistic approach to appraisal to assess the pros and cons of doing said work. Tallman and Work's appraisal selection framework argues to conduct technical and content appraisal on content prior to ingest into digital preservation storage so as to avoid saving everything simply because it is easy or affordable.[36] This calls for intentional management of preservation and derivative copies of data, which underscores the principles of a political/relational model of disability. Making conscionable decisions about how many copies of an item and its derivative forms to store may help with accessibility as we respond to requests for accommodations. For example, an original video file may need captioning and/or transcription for a user. Rather than delete this derivative, we can save both

or replace the old derivative with the captioned version to better serve future requests.

Documentation is a cornerstone of successful archival and preservation practice. The beauty of PREMIS metadata is its flexibility and scalability. When updating or modifying preservation actions on born-digital collections to account for accessibility and inclusion, update the preservation metadata to document these changes and their rationale while protecting the privacy of user data. As new tools are developed and implemented for digital preservation, we should pay close attention to whether systemic and unconscious biases are embedded in their design. Utilizing accessibility auditing tools for computing will help with our assessments to implement these tools.

C. *Accessioning and Processing*

Standards for born-digital accessioning and processing vary among institutions, but they are jointly built upon traditional archival arrangement and description standards, such as the General International Standard Archival Description (ISAD(G)).[25] Additionally, practitioners have collaborated to develop additional frameworks and guidelines that have been widely implemented or used as a model for local practices, such as the UC Born-Digital Processing something and the Born-Digital Access Framework, which both account for accessibility protocols.[4] [5] [7] [18]

Archives often struggle with unprocessed backlogs, and many employ the More-Product, Less-Process methodology to streamline processing and access efforts.[22] However, this standard was created prior to the widescale adoption of born-digital archival practices and cannot always be easily adapted to these formats. Yet just because there are more tools at our disposal to process born-digital records may not necessarily mean it is wise to employ them. Lise Jaillant warns that those processing born-digital records are at risk of increasing their backlog if they do not apply the MPLP methodology to these formats as well.[26] However, the MPLP philosophy did not account for circumnavigating implicit biases of ableism or bigotry and neither does Jaillant's extension to processing born-digital records.[22] [26]

Describing and arranging content for accessioning and processing must remain flexible in order to allow for modifications needed to fulfill accommodation requests. Saving transparent and

accurate documentation alongside the born-digital content helps provide verification of the records' provenance if they have had to undergo transformations. Including processing notes about inaccessibility or insensitivities in the born-digital content can also help queue projects for improving access and use, such as captioning audiovisual materials and/or providing external documentation of transcriptions. When born-digital content already has embedded metadata to work with assistive technologies, design and conduct an audit system which would allow staff to determine the quality of these embedded features.

Some content requires emulation for processing as well as an authentic access method to experience and understand the data. However, emulated environments commonly feature historic and/or obsolete software which is far less likely to have usable assistive technologies or equitable approaches to reducing bigotry in their systems. Thorough documentation about the limitations and potential of emulating content demonstrates a commitment to the critical disability and intersectionality theories which challenge individuals and institutions to correct or prevent harm from these biases. If emulation is the primary processing method for reading content, write up a brief option for additional or modified access methods to these files without relying on the emulator.

Lastly, disclaimers about unintentional harm can go a long way in simply acknowledging the lived experiences of those facing barriers. If it is not feasible to document the idiosyncrasies of all files and systems in collections, a broad statement applied to a collection-level description, such as in the finding aid, can help introduce and warn researchers about what they may encounter.

D. Access and Use

When providing access to materials, users need to have a seamless and obvious ability to make a request for accommodations for born-digital collections. This is especially true when accessing born-digital archives remotely; users are less likely to have immediate help from staff when accessing content online. Additionally, standardizing all access workstations in archival reading rooms with assistive technologies and regularly upgrading them will help anticipate users' needs in advance while simultaneously reducing the need for researchers to disclose disability or identify information. And while

complying with legislation is necessary, nothing is precluding us from being more inclusive than what is classified as a protected class. Implementing additional inclusivity efforts beyond those required by law will further strengthen the trust users have with the archive.

Educating users on their experiences is a key component of promoting ethical use of archival collections, regardless of format. This instruction should extend to biases in computing to disclose the limits of technologies, both historic and current, and provide additional context about the data itself, its technical metadata, its custodial history, and whatever derivative forms it has taken in preservation. When working with born-digital records, we need to provide context about the authenticity of a digital document while simultaneously contextualizing its idiosyncrasies. For example, if a collection includes files that rely on proprietary software, but the request for accommodation requires the files to be migrated to a more accessible file format, we could provide contextual information about our preservation processes as well as the historical context of the files and software. When born-digital files are modified to meet accommodations, we also need to provide them with choices about how to understand the file in context; is it helpful for users to experience the data as close to its original rendering as possible, such as within an emulated environment? Or is it acceptable to receive only the raw data of the item itself? Does the user need access to both forms? Proof of custodial history and provenance may not always be requested by users of born-digital records, but being prepared to provide that information encourages a proactive response to these requests.

Knowing that born-digital archives have the potential for causing harm due to inherent biases rooted in bigotry and ableism, repositories should focus on a user-first approach and prioritize the humanity of users. If possible, develop mechanisms to anticipate needs for your user communities in order to reduce the requirements for them to self-disclose any disabilities or social identities. When users do disclose their disabilities or vulnerabilities, be mindful of how challenging it can be for them to trust a stranger in a position of authority in a cultural heritage institution with this information. We can learn to authentically and actively listen to our users, trust their perspectives, and leverage their feedback.

VIII. DISCUSSION

E. Limitations

As posited originally by Emma May in their comprehensive literature review, there is still much effort needed by archival and library scholars to continue assessing the field from a critical disability lens.[26] Much of the work in this paper is largely theoretical and therefore possible to dispute when measured against real-life scenarios. Therefore, it is imperative for this research to delve further into authentic user experience studies that are focused on disability and marginalized users. Once accurate and reliable data is collected from user studies, there are possibilities for designing updated tools and resources that remediate barriers. Additionally, as a cis-het, able-bodied, and white woman, the author of this paper is incapable of fully understanding or conveying the needs of those in the disability and marginalized communities. Although the research has been attempted with care and respect, there are inherent, limited perspectives that cannot guarantee adequate remediation for those who are disadvantaged as is in alignment with CDT and Intersectionality theories. Therefore, it is further emphasized that user experience studies are conducted to reduce ableist and/or bigoted perspectives as much as possible.

F. Future Research

Future research is also needed from technical assessments to advance a comprehensive understanding of computing capabilities against perceived barriers. For example, emulation is a useful method for processing or accessing some historic collection content as it provides opportunities for data to be rendered as closely as possible to the original ways in which it was created and used.[28] Yet historic operating systems that are emulated are more likely to have implicit biases if they lack software for assistive technologies or if embedded assistive technologies compatible with those systems are not up to current standards for accessibility. However, the resources, knowledge, and time to create emulated environments for accessing born-digital content is often great and is not always necessary.[28] As such, the significant effort to provide emulated access should incorporate research about accessibility standards and the feasibilities to provide accommodations.

Further, thorough testing and documentation on the capabilities of assistive technology software, such as screen readers or transcription tools, is needed on historic or obsolete file formats regardless of whether they are presented in an emulated environment or not. Such testing and knowledge could help archival staff develop a proactive approach to user requests rather than struggling to troubleshoot tools on an impromptu basis.

Another technical perspective that must be studied is how generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tools when preserving, processing, or providing access to born-digital records can improve and/or further disadvantage those from disability or marginalized groups. Although GenAI has been applied to various tools and services with ubiquitousness, there still remains much to discover with its potential for its impacts on archival work. By assessing emulation options, assistive technologies, and GenAI tools, archival staff can develop a service model for accommodation requests by responding to users with transparency about turnaround times, ethical considerations, and limitations of the tools and resources available.

IX. CONCLUSION

Assessing computer history, design, and use from the perspectives of Critical Disability and Intersectionality Theories allows us to acknowledge the complex and ever-evolving challenges embedded in the machines. For the last several decades, computers have been the primary tool for creating and maintaining resources that are important to cultural heritage. Assuming that computers are segregated from the cultures in which they were created will only perpetuate unconscious and systemic harm to users of born-digital archives.

Computers have developed significantly since their invention, but archival and cultural heritage workers must contend with born-digital files from all spans of history and plan for future acquisitions. A continuous evolution in our approaches to digital preservation and born-digital access can mitigate the challenges of historic, current, and future computing biases. As technologies evolve, so will collections; some changes may bring solutions to existing barriers, while others may create new barriers. In contrast, the introduction of new technologies can also reduce barriers created by inherent computer biases. Staying aware of and attentive to these

changes will inform training needs, praxis, and policy. Therefore, continuous education and re-training are vital.

While there will never be one, specific way to provide adequate and equitable preservation of and access to born-digital collections, we can leverage knowledge about technological limitations and biases to improve, repair, and mediate barriers.

REFERENCES

- [1] "ACRL-RBMS/SAA Guidelines on Access to Research Materials in Archives and Special Collections Libraries." White paper, [ACRL](https://www.acrl.org), revised: Jan. 2020, <https://www.ala.org/acrl/standards/jointstatement> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [2] ADA, "Fact Sheet: New Rule on the Accessibility of Web Content and Mobile Apps Provided by State Governments," [ADA](https://www.ada.gov/resources/2024-03-08-web-rule/), Washington, D.C., USA, Apr. 2024, <https://www.ada.gov/resources/2024-03-08-web-rule/> (access Apr. 14, 2025).
- [3] American Library Association, "Assistive Technology," *ALA*, Oct. 2020, <https://www.ala.org/rusa/assistive-technology> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [4] E. Arroyo-Ramirez, K. Bolding, D. Butler, A. Cobourn, B. Dietz, J. Farrell, A. Helms, K. Henke, C. Macquarie, S. Peltzman, C. T. Watson, A. Taylor, J. Venlet, P. Walker, "Levels of Born-Digital Access," *DLF*, Feb. 2020, <https://osf.io/hqmy4> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [5] D. Baker, D. Butler, S. Gentry, L. Riddlesperger, J. Wachtel, and C. Williams, "An Exploration of Access Systems: A Framework for Access Systems for Born-Digital Archival Materials," BDAWG-DLF, Alexandria, VA, USA, Rep., Dec. 2023, <https://osf.io/kecs8/>.
- [6] R. Benjamin, *Race after Technology: Abolitionist Tools for the New Jim Code*. Medford, MA, USA: Polity, 2019.
- [7] A. Berdini, C. Macquarie, S. Peltzman, and K. Tasker, "UC Guidelines for Born-Digital Archival Description," *UC-BDCKG GitHub*, 2017, <https://github.com/uc-borndigital-ckg/uc-guidelines> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [8] W. Blanzeisky P. Cunningham, "Algorithmic Factors Influencing Bias in Machine Learning," in *ECML PKDD 2021*, (Virtual), 2021. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-93736-2_41.
- [9] G. Brilmyer, "Archival assemblages: applying disability studies' political/relational model to archival description," *Arch. Sci.*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 95-118, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s10502-018-9287-6.
- [10] G. Brilmyer and C. Lee, "Terms of use: Crip legibility in information systems," *First Monday*, vol. 28, no. 1-2, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.5210/fm.v28i1.12935.
- [11] S. Burgstahler, "Working Together: People with Disabilities and Computer Technology," *Do-It*, 2022, <https://www.washington.edu/doi/working-together-people-disabilities-and-computer-technology> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [12] R. G. S. Carter, "Of Things Said and Unsaid: Power, Archival Silences, and Power in Silence," *Archivaria*, vol. 61, pp. 215-233, Sep. 2006, <https://archivaria.ca/index.php/archivaria/article/view/12541>.
- [13] J. Clark and Z. Lischer-Katz, "(In)accessibility and the technocratic library: Addressing institutional failures in library adoption of emerging technologies," *First Monday*, vol. 28, no. 1-2, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.5210/fm.v28i1.12928.
- [14] A. Cooke, "A History of Accessibility at IBM." *AccessWorld* 5, Mar. 2004, <https://www.afb.org/aw/5/2/14760>.
- [15] K. Crenshaw, "Mapping the margins: intersectionality, identity politics, and violence against women of color," *Stanf. Law Rev.*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 1241-1299, Jul. 1991, doi: 10.2307/1229039.
- [16] Department of Economic and Social Affairs Disability, "Disability Laws and Acts by Country/Area," *Uni. Nat.*, <https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/disability-laws-and-acts-by-country-area.html> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [17] *Digital Preservation Handbook*, 2nd ed., Digital Preservation Coalition, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook>.
- [18] J. Farrell, B. Dietz, and A. Clemens, "Digital Library Federation Born-Digital Access Working Group Access Values," *OSF*, Sep. 2020, <https://osf.io/https://osf.io/dzhcp>.
- [19] B. Friedman and H. Nissenbaum, "Bias in computer systems," *ACM Trans. Inf. Syst.*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 330-347, Jul. 1996, doi: 10.1145/230538.230561.
- [20] A. Gibson and J. Martin III, "Re-situating information poverty: Information marginalization and parents of individuals with disabilities," *J. Assoc. Inf. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 70, no. 5, pp. 476-487, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1002/asi.24128.
- [21] M. A. Greene, "Improving Accessibility for People with Disabilities," *Arch. Out.*, Dec. 2010, <http://files.archivists.org/periodicals/Archival-Outlook/Back-Issues/2010-6-AO.pdf> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [22] M. A. Greene and D. Meissner, "More Product, Less Process: Revamping Traditional Archival Processing," *Amer. Arch.*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 208-263, Fall 2005, doi: 10.17723/aarc.68.2.c741823776k65863.
- [23] M. C. Hall, "Critical Disability Theory," *Stan. Ency. of Phil.*, Wint. 2019, Edward N. Zalta (ed.), <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2019/entries/disability-critical/> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [24] M. Hicks, *Programmed Inequality: How Britain Discarded Women Technologists and Lost Its Edge in Computing*, 1st ed. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, 2017.
- [25] ISAD(G): General International Standard Archival Description, ICA Standard, 2nd Edition, 1999. Available:

<https://www.ica.org/resource/isadg-general-international-standard-archival-description-second-edition/>

- [26] L. Jaillant, "More Data, Less Process: A User-Centered Approach to Email and Born-Digital Archives," *Amer. Arch.*, vol. 85, no. 2, pp. 533-555, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.17723/2327-9702-85.2.533.
- [27] Joint Archives Management / Records Management Roundtables Working Group on Accessibility in Archives and Records Management. "Best Practices for Working with Archives Researchers with Physical Disabilities." White paper, SAA, Aug. 2010, https://www2.archivists.org/sites/all/files/BestPract-Disabilities_Researchers_0.pdf (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [28] E. Kaltman, W. Schwaid-Lindner, D. Jonathan, A. Borman, A. Garnett, and L. Masinter, "An Overview of Emulation as a Preservation Method," CLIR, Alexandria, VA, USA, no. 194, 2025.
- [29] A. Koenecke, A. Nam, E. Lake, J. Nudell, M. Quartey, Z. Mengesha, C. Troups, J.R. Rickford, D. Jurafsky, and S. Goel, "Racial disparities in automated speech recognition," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* Vol. 117, no. 14, 2020, pp. 7684-7689, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1915768117.
- [30] *Levels of Digital Preservation*, National Digital Stewardship Alliance, Oct. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/>.
- [31] D. Luster, "Archives Have the Power to Boost Marginalized Voices," *TEDxPittsburgh*, Jun. 2018, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XsNPIBBI1IE> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [32] E. May, "Interrogating access: a critical disability studies approach to information practices research," *J. Doc.*, vol. 81, no. 2, pp. 438-455, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.1108/JD-05-2024-0117.
- [33] D. E. McCrea, "Creating a More Accessible Environment for Our Users with Disabilities: Responding to an Office for Civil Rights Complaint." *Arch. Iss.*, vol. 38, no. 1, 2017, pp. 7-18, doi: 10.31274/archivalissues.11029.
- [34] I. Moura, "Encoding normative ethics: On algorithmic bias and disability," *First Monday*, vol. 28, no. 1-2, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.5210/fm.v28i1.12905.
- [35] Reference, Access & Outreach Section Steering Committee, "Guidelines for Accessible Archives for People with Disabilities," SAA, Feb. 2019, <https://www2.archivists.org/groups/reference-access-and-outreach-section/guidelines-for-accessible-archives-for-people-with-disabilities> (accessed Apr. 14, 2025).
- [36] N. Tallman and L. Work, "Approaching Appraisal: Framing criteria for selecting digital content for preservation," in *iPRES 2018*, (Boston, MA), 2018, doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/8Y6DC.
- [37] "Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 1.0," W3C. <https://www.w3.org/TR/WAI-WEBCONTENT/>

- [38] B. Wentz, U. Gorham, and P. T. Jaeger, "Academic libraries and their legal obligation for content accessibility," *First Monday*, vol. 28, no. 1-2, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.5210/fm.v28i1.12892.

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